

The IMPROVE Checklist for Intervention: A Complete Guide

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Introduction

This document is designed to guide police officers through the effective use of the **IMPROVE Project Checklist for Intervention in Domestic Violence**. The checklist is not just a list of tasks but a procedural tool to ensure a consistent, safe, and legally sound response. Following these steps will help you systematically gather crucial information, secure evidence, and provide immediate support to the victim. Its objective is to ensure that all essential steps and relevant information are considered and documented during an intervention in cases of domestic and gender-based violence.

What the Checklist Focuses On:

- ✓ **Standardization of Procedures:** Ensuring all officers follow the same systematic steps during an intervention.
- ✓ **Comprehensive Documentation:** Guaranteeing that all essential information and evidence are collected for legal purposes.
- ✓ **Victim-Centric Approach:** Prioritizing the safety and empowerment of the victim by providing resources and protection measures.
- ✓ **Risk Assessment:** Enabling officers to identify immediate threats and assess the level of danger posed by the aggressor.
- ✓ **Inter-Agency Communication:** Facilitating the timely transfer of information to specialized units and support services.

The list was developed as a best practice by the GAMA team of the Spanish IMPROVE project partner *Policía Local de Valencia (PLV)*. The GAMA group was created in 2003 as a specific task force for domestic violence, working as a decentralised but coordinated unit. Since 2016 it has been formed by more than 30 police officers who are specifically trained and experienced, working exclusively in this field. They carry out awareness campaigns as well and work with an internal system for criminal profiling to better design further intervention programmes. More than 20.000 victims have been protected since its beginning and more than 1.200 victims are being protected nowadays.

Checklist for printing:

You can download the checklist in English and Spanish [HERE](#).

Checklist example:

IMPROVE Project: Checklist for Intervention in Domestic and Gender-Based Violence

Objective: Ensure that all essential steps and relevant information are considered and documented during an intervention in cases of domestic and gender-based violence.

I. Arrival at the Scene and Initial Inspection

- Conduct a visual inspection of the scene.
- Take photographic evidence (if necessary)

II. Private Interview with the victim

- Record the badge/ID number of the officer conducting the interview in the report
- Ask if this is the first violent incident.
- Collect information on previous episodes of violence
- Ask if the victim has medical reports, medical care records, or previous complaints.
- Make photocopies and attach them to the Report (if applicable).
- Ask if there are witnesses to the incident (present or not) or to previous episodes of violence.
- Obtain full details and telephone numbers of witnesses.
- Ask if the alleged aggressor possesses firearms
- Provisionally seize firearms (if applicable).
- Draft a Record of firearm seizure.
- State in the Report the location of the weapons, pending transfer to storage Verify if the victim presents injuries.
- Request a specific medical report.
- Take photographic evidence of the victim
- Draft a Record (if applicable).

III. Collection of Data and Additional Information

- Gather information from the complainant, neighbours, and other witnesses
- Fully identify the complainant.
- Reference the neighbours' doors (if applicable)

IV. Essential Data for the Statement

- Record the place of aggression (home, public space, etc.)
- Indicate if minors witnessed the incident or were present at the scene
- Record whether weapons were used
- Indicate if the aggressor had any restraining or precautionary measures (e.g., restraining order)
- Record the aggressor's exact words to the victim (in quotation marks)
- Describe the emotional state of the victim and the aggressor as observed by the officers.
- Assess the subjective risk (aggressor violent, intoxicated, etc.)

V. Documentation to Attach to the Report

- Photocopy of medical assistance (specific report)
- Photographic report of the residence (if carried out)
- Photographic report of the victim (if carried out).
- Photocopies in the victim's possession of previous complaints, rulings, court orders, or medical reports (if any)
- Record of firearm seizure (if carried out)
- Request for a protection order (if completed)
- Offer a protection order to every victim, especially if there are minor children in common.

VI. Delivery of Informative Documents to the Victim

- Provide the victim with the Basic Guide of Resources and Self-Protection Measures.

VII. Drafting of the Service Report

- Draft the Service Report.

VIII. Copy to the specialized unit on DV

- Send a copy to the specialized unit on DV.

IX. Follow up: evaluation of the intervention

- 2 months after the intervention
- 6 months after the intervention

This checklist may be printed and used in each intervention to ensure consistency and thoroughness of procedures.

About the IMPROVE Project:

Domestic violence is a massive problem across Europe. Many victims don't reach out for help due to fear, shame, a lack of information, or language barriers.

IMPROVE aims to change this. This EU project helps empower victims by ensuring they know and can exercise their rights to protection and support. A key part of the project is the development of AinoAid™, a multilingual AI chatbot that offers anonymous and accessible assistance to victims and their relatives.

IMPROVE also supports the police and other first responders in using their capabilities effectively, allowing protective measures to be implemented more quickly and improving collaboration between different sectors. Through targeted campaigns, the project raises public awareness and promotes dialogue among various stakeholders.

Here are the 4 main goals of **IMPROVE**:

1. **Help via a Chatbot:** An AI chatbot is designed to make it easier for victims of domestic violence to find the right contact person and get help.
2. **Faster Implementation:** The project helps the police and other authorities implement protective measures against domestic violence more quickly and effectively.
3. **Improved Collaboration:** First responders (such as police officers, social workers, and medical staff) will be able to collaborate more effectively through training to help victims more efficiently.
4. **More Knowledge for Everyone:** The public should be educated about domestic violence so that victims know where to find help. At the same time, helpers should also gain a better understanding of the victims' situation.

Learn more at <https://www.improve-horizon.eu/>!